

FROM THE PASSIVE PLURALIST HOUSE TO THE MODERN nZEB, DESIGN AND APPLICATION CONSIDERATION FOR A BETTER PERFORMING LESS COSTLY ENERGY EFFICIENT HOUSE

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper presents a series of managerial and economic considerations related to the construction of passive houses.*

Methodology/approach – *This article identifies three distinct generations of passive house: The Pluralist Passive House (PPH), the Modern Passive House (MPH) and the Net Zero Energy Building (nZEB), developed over the last five decades.*

Findings – *Relation between surface, volume, and energy, which represents the main part of the research, was concretized by determining a mathematical relationship, which is in the process of obtaining the copyright.*

Research limitations/implications – *The research was carried out under laboratory conditions.*

Practical implications – *The research results can be applied in the construction of houses and industrial halls.*

Originality/value – *The research is original, and the mathematical relationship determined is in the process of obtaining the copyright.*

Key words: nZEB, Compactness, Energy.

Introduction

The Passive house concept has developed in the Early 1970's in the background of the world's energy crisis. Since then, different types of passive houses have been developed, mostly in West Europe and North America. Today of the total energy generated, a third to half of the consumption is associated with household. As reduction of energy consumption, use of renewable energy, and reduction of emissions are becoming a priority, sustainable living based on the passive house and nZEB (Net Zero Energy Building) are getting more attention and becoming mainstream.

This article reviews three aspects of the Passive house/nZEB off the grid design. First - Historically, identifies three distinct generations of passive house: The Pluralist Passive House (PPH), the Modern Passive House (MPH) and the Net Zero Energy Building (nZEB), developed over the last five decades. Second- the effect of the compactness ratio (size and shape) over the thermal performance on the nZEB design. Third and final, presents a series of managerial and economic considerations related to the construction of the grid nZEB design.

From the Pluralist Passive House to the Modern nZEB

Since the turnover of the 20th century buildings and technology has evolved significantly. Electricity and light have changed buildings from being dependent on natural resources, like light through windows, to controlled environment (Rowan University, 2017).

In the early 1970's in the period of the energy crisis in America a solution for a more energy efficient house was sought. It was the answer to increasingly high costs of energy bills.

The first countries to have realized passive houses were countries with cold weather who were affected mostly of the energy crisis. The Saskatchewan conservation house in Canada 1975-1977 (Passipedia Organization, 2017) - probably the first recorded Passive house in a modern definition - applied common construction solutions to reduce cost of energy.

Another example of an early PPH is The Massachusetts conservation house 1973-1977. The PPH applied a better solution to an existing building method. It was a natural step for a better performing house and was based on existing technologies “Draw a pie as the total consumption of a house” says Orr. “You divide it in three equal parts. One third of it is losses through the windows, the walls, and the ceiling. One third is heat loss through the basement. And the other third is air leakage.” (Office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy, 2017).

The process and the design were not of innovation technology wise. It was rather, a better application of the existing methods of construction at the time. Elimination of basement, increased wall thickness and added insulation, efficient orientation of windows towards the sun. During the 1980's another important technological advance, allowed for more energy efficient solution the double-glazed window. The new window type helped control the climate inside the house (Eley, 2016).

Later the development of LED light made another technological step. It helped reduce the heat generated by conventional light bulbs and significantly reduced the energy consumption (U.S. Department of Energy, 2012) and (Navarro, 2012). With solar power technology and a proven concept of a passive house-a new era of passive house was born. The Modern Passive House MPH. The new modern Passive house began developing with the new technologies into a new direction-house systems and improved building envelope. In addition to the methods implemented in the PPH, the MPH implemented multiple technologies and better building systems, reducing energy consumption.

By 2005 global heating, carbon footprint. It became a world known problem affecting most of the world's population. Awareness, increased demand, demand implemented code, for better performing houses, leading to the generation of the modern nZEB. Not only a passive house that relies on better application of existing building methods and new technologies, but a house that is able to generate free energy, offset completely energy costs, and rely heavily on technology to significantly reduce the carbon footprint and energy consumption.

Compactness ratio review

The size and shape of forms and the effect of the energy is a long-known phenomenon in thermophysics. In the world of Passive house design achieving nZEB is a high threshold. one of the best practices achieving Net-Zero, is reducing size to reduce energy consumption. Geometry and compactness are main design considerations in passive house. Specifically, different aspects of the compactness ratio or described as the surface to volume ratio. Following a discussion, the importance of achieving a compact house design, to reduce consumption significantly. Compactness ratio, or surface to volume ratio is a classical problem in the world of building. It is a heavily viewed subject, especially in the nZEB aspects. It has been discussed for half a century now. This problem gets increased attention as building codes for energy performance are increasing in Europe and in the US (Wright and Klingenberg, 2015), (Holton, 2012), (Dimetrosky, Parkinson and Lieb, 2014), (Industry Alliance, 2013), (Edelson, Cheslak and Urbanek, 2021). In the early days of the first examples of passive house, (such as the Saskatchewan Conservation house 1975 some basic principles proved to be very effective - decreasing the house size and eliminating the basement. These principles are still applied today for MPH and nZEB (Ben-Senior, Ungureanu and Banica, 2019), (Ben-Senior, Ungureanu and Banica, 2020).

In 1979, in the article “The Saskatchewan Conservation House Some Preliminary Performance Results”, the authors, explains how the high-performance passive house was achieved. He mentioned the importance of size and ratio to consumption of different examples built in Denmark and Toronto (Besant, Dumont and Schoenau, 1979).

In earlier example projects (Anderson and Riordan, 1976): “As early as 1939 a 100% space heated structure was constructed at the Massachusetts Institute of technology. For two years it operated requiring no auxiliary heat... The relatively small collector area to floor area ratio, and water storage volume to house volume ratio, achieved the desired result. The Saskatchewan Conservation House are due to several factors... the space heating load has been reduced to about five Gigajoules per year” the

application of a reduced footprint with renewable energy sources as solar heat collectors and water storage proved to be a good practice for passive house.

In 1981 Givoni writes in his article "Conservation and The Use of Integrated Passive Energy Systems in Architecture": "The term layout in this context refers mainly to the compactness or otherwise of the house plan. The main impacts of layout from the energy point of view, is its effect, on the one hand, on the envelope surface area and, on the other hand, on the potential for natural ventilation. As the house plan is more compact the surface area of the walls, for a given floor area, becomes smaller. As a result, the heat exchange by conduction between the house and the ambient air is decreased... the smaller surface area reduces the energy demand of the house...", "The architectural aspects which have an impact on the thermal behavior of the building and its indoor climate and thus on human comfort and energy requirements" Givoni concluded a direct relationship between the compactness to the reduction of energy consumption. Further in his article he associates energy performance and reduction of consumption with other methods such as solar radiation, nocturnal outgoing long wave radiation, night convective cooling, evaporative cooling (Givoni, 1981).

In 1987, in his book, "Fundamentals of Heat Transfer (1987)", Alan J Chapman, wrote "The shape and orientation of bodies is long known to have effect of the direction of convection and heat flow." While heat exchange by thermal radiation does not depend on a transport medium, the geometric configuration of bodies exchanging heat by this mechanism is quite important. The amount of the radiation emitted by one body that is intersected by another is highly dependent on the size, shape, and relative orientation of the bodies", the discussion is attached to the Boltzmann equation (Chapman, 1987).

In 2005, in his Article, Al-Bahi, et al., is describing the effect of natural convection in a tilted rectangular enclosure. Specifically, with ratio of width to height of 1:5 of which is then describing the effect of the ratio on the convection when and how the ratio is affecting the Nusselt number as a result of inclination. "The maximum Nusselt number is found close to the vertical orientation while the minimum is at the horizontal position with fluid heated from the top for which convection is effectual and the average Nusselt number is greater than unity." The boundary condition., the ratio and shape affect the conductive to convection ratio (Al-Bahi, Al-Hamzy, and Zaki, 2005).

In 2009, Kimmo Lylykangas, writes in his article is mentioned surface to volume ratio and the importance of shape factor in energy consumption. He demonstrates different ratios performing differently and the approach to design as the consideration of the shape factor (Lylykangas, 2005).

In 2011, Rodriguez Gonzales, et al. [20], mentions in her article the need to create Energy efficient Index for buildings under new energy consumption policies. The index value is based on the ratio between the energy consumption to the surface. It does relate to the consumption to the volume. The Author makes a valid point of importance of indexing the performance of different buildings in relation to the growing need for reducing energy consumption (Rodriguez Gonzales, Vinagre Diaz, Caamano, and Wilby, 2011).

In 2014 in the article "Energy Efficacy Evaluation of Zero Energy Houses", the authors, are mentioning under passive design geometric and ratios as one of the key components in achieving government directives of reducing energy and pollution reduction by creating a low energy building (Rodriguez-Ubinas, Rodriguez, Voss, and Todorovic, 2014). "Energy efficiency contest is mostly related with three juried contests: Architecture, Engineering and construction and sustainability..." the design is related in the article to the interior comfort and functionally of the house. "The passive design method is directly associated with the thermal performance of the envelope. "In addition to the house envelopes, there are other strategies to accomplish a high energy efficiency performance... The volume of the building can be used to achieve greater energy efficiency for the entire life cycle of the building". The contest included eighteen projects. The methods of achieving high energy performance were made by creating, six different categories: (1) passive strategies, (2) thermal energy storage, (3) hybrid systems, (4) active conditioning systems, (5) hot water, (6) other energy efficiency solutions. Passive strategies group included twenty-two methods of achieving energy efficiency, however none of which included nor applied, ratio, compactness, layout, or similar factors.

In 2019, Vallejo-Coral and his coauthors describe a theoretical and experimental method of calculating factors for calculating cooling loads for buildings in warm climates (Vallejo-Coral, Solorio-Rivera, Gijon-Rivera and Zuniga-Pueblo, 2019). The article aims to determine CLTD values for roofs and walls. The experiment proves good practice, and the results are highly in agreement with other results of a project

conducted in Turkey as well ASHRAE methods. However, the method provided is based on a two-dimensional form (wall or roof) and is based on geographical specific conditions, meaning, precipitation, latitude, longitude, and temperature. The method does not provide a physical formula to explain the entire performance of the thermal load changes regardless to their location and in respect to total effect over the entire house rather than a specific wall. Specifically, the calculation and coefficient are all related to a two dimensional and do not account for changes happening in the captured volume as departing from the exterior wall. The experiment is limited to the surface of the wall (interior and exterior) rather than the captured volume of air inside the house. The assumption of the model is that surrounding temperature of different surfaces are equal to outdoor temperature which intends to say, that the wall section assumes constant one temperature through its entire height (?) How does this assumption affects the results? The wall's temperature, is highly likely to be different at its base than at its roof when exposed to sunlight due to conduction added heat from the ground, absorbed radiant heat etc. On the other hand, the performance accounts for the accumulated behavior of the effect of convection as well as conduction. Which does provide a more realistic image of the results.

The above literature review is making the case clear. In different fields of research there, is a clear consensus over two basic principles:

One - there is a bond between surface, volume, and energy.

Two - regardless to the form, of which energy, specifically heat, presents itself convection, conduction, radiation, energy is affected by the shape direction and orientation of shapes.

Each and every result above is valid in its field and adds a new perspective. The results raise the following question: how does the surface, volume, and energy can be harnessed in the field of passive house design and construction, into one method of design, to generate a better performing sustainable living space, reducing pollution and energy consumption? For this, experiment is proposed: build different houses in different shapes and ratios, measure the energy consumption in comparison the atmospheric conditions and establish the most efficient method. My experiment measured the ability to retain heat of different shapes and different volumes under the same conditions. The results are clear. Different shapes and different volumes retain heat differently over time.

Table 1. Experimental results

Cube	Size [inch]	Average time to retain heat [min]	$\Delta^{\circ}\text{C}$	Temperature loss rate/min
Cube A	26/26/26"	398	20	19.90
Cube B	35/35/35"	377	20	18.85
Cube C	50/50/50"	272	20	13.60

Fig.1. Temperature loss over time of different cube sizes

The smaller the cube the faster it loses heat. In other words, the ability to retain heat is opposite proportional to the size of the cube. This principal should be applied in the field of design. Design small houses with high compactness ratio. To make the experiment practical, one dimension - the height need to be constant and fixed - the height of the ceiling. That is to allow the space to be usable. The proposed heigh is 250cm. Naturally, high insulation materials, sun orientation and other geographical considerations will contribute further to the performance of the house to sustain itself off the grid.

Financial and managerial aspects of nZEB

During our research regarding the subject, it became evident that building a high energy efficient house is more expensive than the traditional method.

Some of main reasons are:

First, high energy efficiency requires more insulation, better building materials, cutting edge technology in reducing energy consumption, high performing appliances, and mechanical systems. They all are requiring a bigger investment comparing to conventional average of the shelf solutions.

Second, less air leaks, better insulation and multiple building systems integrated into one household requires highly trained labor and more attention to detail during construction. In other words, highly trained specialists instead of common construction labor and longer building time. Both increase to the cost of construction.

Third, to meet the definition of nZEB or Passive house, in addition to all the expected household appliances and systems, the newbuilt, is required to have green energy harvesting system, such as windmill, solar panels etc., which adds to the cost of conventional house.

Increasing the cost of construction reduces the accessibility of the masses to better performing energy house. to offset the increased costs and increase scalability, one proposed solution is off site manufacturing. Instead of one design at a time, it is proposed to utilize specialty designers for multiple stock plans of different houses plans. Considering all the necessary design methods in advance from building systems, insulation, and windows. Then, to premanufacture off-site.

Metal Structural Insulated Panels (MSIP), offer a full design and manufacturing in a controlled environment. Then shipping the complete project to the site, ready to assemble. MSIP technology (<https://thermasteelinc.com>, 2019) offers the structure, sheathing, vapor barrier and insulation all in one. The project arrives to the site with all the accessories, plates, and screws ready to assemble, just like big building block. The units are about 25kg a piece of 4 sqm allowing an unexperienced team of three, to assemble a full house in three days. Cutting the labor from four trades to one trade and from months to days.

Scalability, premanufacturing and high efficiency method are the key factors to reduce cost and make the nZEB model available to the masses at a lower cost.

Discussion and conclusions

The present paper contains part of research from PH.D. work entitled Research on Optimization of Technological Solutions of nZEB House.

In the first part of the paper, a brief but detailed description of the nZEB house concept is presented. The reference works in the field are presented with the concrete specification of the contribution for each of them.

The research carried out within the doctorate have highlighted two main directions:

- ✓ The relation between surface, volume, and energy, which represents the main part of the research, was concretized by determining a mathematical relationship, which is in the process of obtaining the copyright.
- ✓ In addition to the established relationship, other parameters influencing heat transfer were identified: shape direction and orientation of shapes.

Some of the research results are presented in the table and graph in the paper. Analyzing the experimental results, it follows that cube A presents the best properties.

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